

Dual Effect of Income Diversification and Digital Transformation on Banks' Profitability in Asian Countries

Thi Thuy Hang Le ¹, and Le Tuan Hiep ^{2*}

¹Lecturer, Banking and Finance Faculty, University of Finance - Marketing (UFM), 84, Vietnam

Email: ltt.hang@ufm.edu.vn; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0684-5974>

²Chairman, University of Finance and Business Administration (UFBA), 84, Vietnam

*Corresponding author email: hiep.lt@ufba.edu.vn; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9996-3437>

Abstract

Background: Income diversification and digital economic transformation are inevitable trends in banking activities today, in line with the development of technology and customer needs; further diversifying income increases a bank's financial efficiency and has the power to positively regulate other factors towards increasing profitability.

Objective: The purpose of the study was to provide more empirical evidence on the digital impact on the economy, whether high-tech sectors increase the business performance of banks or not. An empirical examination of the dual effect of income diversification and digital transformation on banks' profitability.

Methodology: This study uses the vector autoregressive panel model (PVAR) according to generalized method of moments (GMM) regression to examine the causal relationship between the digital transformation of the economy and income diversification, including the promotion of non-interest income and profits in the business performance of banks in Asian countries.

Result: The research results show that when the economy increases investment in financial technology, it will support the business activities of banks; digital technology has positive impacts on non-interest income but accounts for an enormous cost in the investment phase, so it does not have much effect on the business performance of banks in Asia.

Conclusion: The authors also found that the results supported banks in considering investment policies in digital technology to bring good business performance but not affect banks' profits.

Unique Contribution: This study illuminates the precarious equilibrium between banks' profitability and the hefty upfront costs of digitization and offers crucial insights into how investments in financial technology generate non-interest income.

Key Recommendation: Financial institutions should design digital services with the client in mind, prioritizing ease of use, accessibility, and convenience. As a result, digital product engagement and customer satisfaction can rise, boosting profitability and enhancing digitalization efforts in the banking industry with incentives and policies.

Keywords: Income diversification; digital transformation; economy; profitability of banks.

Introduction

The digital transformation process in the bank's business operations helps to enhance banking operations by providing customers with products and services using the bank's technology and digital platforms. Digital transformation supports improving the efficiency of banks' business operations and increasing the competitiveness of banks in serving customers (Acharya & Steffen, 2020). Digital transformation also contributes to conveniently expanding the connection between banks and customers. From there, the business operations of banks also create a diverse and rich ecosystem with many channels to meet customers' needs. At the same time, it contributes to increasing non-interest income for banks and reducing risks when focusing too much on the bank's credit activities (Mirzaei et al., 2024).

The motivation for the study is to increase the diversification of banking activities from interest-based activities to non-core income-based activities for a bank to stay in business. Banks engage in different activities, such as investments, transactions, and remittances, through which non-core income is earned; therefore, the non-core income ratio of commercial banks increases. Banking operations in emerging markets experienced a decline in traditional operations, forcing them to diversify into new business strategies (Aguayo & Ślusarczyk, 2020; Borio, 2020). The increase in banks' non-core income activities is also attributed to the 2008 global financial crisis, increased competition among banks, technological advances, and financial innovations, allowing banks to offer their customers a broader range of services and products. Information and communications technology developments, such as the Internet, impact banks' level and type of non-core income. Therefore, the study aims to provide more empirical evidence on the digital impact on the economy, whether high-tech sectors increase the business performance of banks or not. An empirical examination of the dual effect of income diversification and digital transformation on banks' profitability.

Theoretical Framework

Income diversification affecting the profitability of banks

Banks can increase their profitability by diversifying their revenue streams away from interest and toward non-interest income sources, including service fees, investment returns, and remittances (Mirzaei et al., 2024). This change is significant for risk management and profitability during economic instability or falling loan activity. Banks can achieve more consistent revenue streams by diversifying their income sources and reducing their reliance on interest rate and credit risk fluctuations (Syadullah, 2018).

Important methods by which a bank's bottom line can be risk Mitigation: Banks can lessen their exposure to market volatility and credit failures by diversifying their income streams away from lending. Thanks to this diversification, banks can keep their income streams consistent even in lean economic times (Moudud-Ul-Huq et al., 2018; Mirzaei et al., 2024). More money comes in from fees from digital banking service fees, asset management commissions, and transaction processing fees, which are all examples of non-interest income that banks can exploit to increase their bottom line.

Banks can increase their profitability through increased client acquisition and retention competitiveness by diversifying their product and service offerings. Paying the price by investing in digital technology and infrastructure is a common requirement for income diversification, but it can ultimately pay off. Meanwhile, the trick is keeping expenses in check so that the rise in non-interest revenue helps boost profits (Öhman & Yazdanfar, 2018).

A bank's ability to streamline operations and boost efficiency through digital platforms for service delivery is directly correlated to the diversity of its revenue streams. Reducing operating costs while keeping or increasing income is one way this operational efficiency can increase profitability (Bömer & Maxin, 2018). A bank's bottom line can benefit from income diversification in some ways, including less reliance on interest income, improved risk management, and the introduction of new revenue streams from fee-based and digital services. How successfully banks handle the expenses linked to these new revenue sources will determine the efficacy of this diversification.

Moudud-UI-Huq et al. (2018) showed that income diversification, especially developing services that generate non-interest income, has helped banks in developing countries reduce risks in business operations and improve competitiveness. The results also show that Indonesian and Thai banks, when diversifying different sources of income, have had positive supporting effects on risk management and business performance of banks in Malaysia, banks are diversifying their income sources to reduce risks from credit activities, contributing to improving the efficiency of banks' business operations in expanding the provision of products and services on the digital transformation platform (Khan et al., 2017). The dependence on income from credit activities is still quite significant in banks. Therefore, non-interest income sources are unimportant in banks' business activities (Belás et al., 2016). Asian banks diversify non-interest assets and services unrelated to lending to increase profits (AlKhoury & Arouri, 2019; Syadullah, 2018).

Income diversity may hurt banks by increasing systemic risk based on models of income diversification's role in banks' systemic risk, which has been developed recently. Yang et al. (2020) examined how income diversification affects banking system risk. According to 2000-2013 US commercial bank data, income diversity increases systemic risk. However, revenue diversification significantly affects systemic risk in large and medium-sized banks. These consequences were significant throughout the 2007-2009 and 2010-2013 credit crises. The European debt crisis showed that bank income diversification reduced systemic risk.

Digital transformation of the economy is affecting the profitability of banks

The introduction of technology innovations that improve operational efficiency, customer experience, and income streams substantially impacts banks' profitability due to the digital transformation of the economy. Digital transformation has many benefits, but it also has drawbacks that banks must handle with care, such as high investment costs and security threats (Khan et al., 2017; Kasman & Kasman, 2016). The following are some ways digital transformation impacts banks' bottom lines. More effectiveness with less expenditure, based on the banks, may save money on transaction fees, cut down on human labour, and simplify their operations using digital platforms and automation.

Digital banking platforms have improved customer service experience by allowing banks to provide more tailored services, easier account access, faster transactions, and round-the-clock availability (Kozak, 2021; Li et al., 2021). Revenue is boosted through higher service usage and fee-based income due to better customer satisfaction and retention brought about by this improved

customer experience. Mobile banking, online payment services, and fintech partnerships are just a few examples of how digital transformation allows banks to diversify their revenue streams beyond interest. The fees and commissions generated by these services can significantly enhance banks' overall profitability (Mateev et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2020). The study by Mawutor et al. (2023) examined the risks and adverse risks that banks face in diversifying income sources and is based on the digital transformation platform of banks. Banks need to develop appropriate strategies for diversifying income, especially non-interest income, and carry out digital transformation safely for the management process to avoid risks in business operations. The study shows that the capital business measures the risk tolerance index of Santander Bank, Spain. This result is the basis for considering whether income diversification, especially developing non-interest income sources, is vital for the bank's risk (Addai et al., 2022).

Bömer and Maxin (2018) studied the role and impact of digital transformation on the business performance of banks in the context of intense economic globalization; the integration trend also contributes to the faster transformation speed of banks. Digitalising business activities aims to support banks in providing products and services safely and quickly while expanding the bank's non-interest income activities (Duho et al., 2021; Belás et al., 2016). However, unlike banks with strong financial potential, small-scale banks face difficulties investing in digital transformation because they must pay a large amount of money in the early stages. In fact, digital transformation brings many benefits to customers and banks, such as faster transaction processing speed. Customers can make transactions without being limited by geographical space and time (Duho et al., 2019).

Research Data and Methodology

Research Data: The data was from 2006 to 2021 and covered 39 Asian countries. Data is taken from the World Bank (WB): <https://databank.worldbank.org/home.aspx>.

Methodology: GMM Estimation of Panel VAR Models based on the reviewed studies, the authors built research models of the survey has 6 variables, specifically Bank return on assets, in percent (ROA); Bank return on equity, in percent (ROE); Bank liquid assets to deposits and short-term funding (LA); Bank non-interest income to total income, in percent (NII); Broadband internet subscribers, in thousands (BIS); Mobile phone subscribers, in millions (MBS).

The vector autoregressive panel model (PVAR) is a model that uses the impulse response function and variance decomposition to examine the causal relationship between variables (Mirzaei et al., 2024; Syadullah, 2018; Li et al., 2021). The model has the form:

$$Y_{i,t} = \mu_i + \sum_{l=1}^p A_l Y_{i,t-l} + B x_{i,t} + C s_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

$y_{i,t} \in \mathfrak{R}^m$ be an $m \times 1$ vector of variables of the regression model of the i -th order at time t .

$y_{i,t-l} \in \mathfrak{R}^m$ be an $m \times 1$ vector lag of regressors.

$x_{i,t} \in \mathfrak{R}^k$ be a $k \times 1$ vector of predetermined variables potentially correlated with past errors.

$s_{i,t} \in \mathfrak{R}^n$ be an $n \times 1$ vector of strictly exogenous variables that neither depends on $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ nor on $\varepsilon_{i,t-s}$ for $s = 1, \dots, T$.

The idiosyncratic error vector $\varepsilon_{i,t} \in \mathfrak{R}^m$ is assumed to be well-behaved and independent from the regressors $x_{i,t}$ and $s_{i,t}$ and the individual error component μ_i .

Describe the model's variables: The research object focuses on studying the interactive relationship between the non-interest income of banks and the level of digital transformation of the economy

on the performance of banks in Asia. The study has six variables, specifically bank return on assets, in percent (ROA); Bank return on equity, in percent (ROE); Bank liquid assets to deposits and short-term funding (LA); Bank non-interest income to total income, in percent (NII); Broadband internet subscribers, in thousands (BIS); Mobile phone subscribers, in millions (MBS). The data was taken by year from 2006 to 2021 and covered 39 Asian countries. Data is taken from the World Bank (WB): <https://databank.worldbank.org/home.aspx>.

Study Results

Apply the Dickey-Fuller unit root test method to test stationarity for the series ROA, ROE, LA, NII, BIS, and MBS, respectively, as shown in Table 1:

Table 1: Model tests for stationarity of data series

Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistics	t-Statistic	Prob.*	St. difference
Null Hypothesis H1: ROA has a unit root	-8.8920	0.0000	d = 0
Null Hypothesis H2: ROE has a unit root	-8.2254	0.0000	d = 0
Null Hypothesis H3: LA has a unit root	-4.0999	0.0000	d = 0
Null Hypothesis H4: NII has a unit root	-6.7900	0.0000	d = 0
Null Hypothesis H5: BIS has a unit root	-20.2826	0.0000	d = 0
Null Hypothesis H6: MBS has a unit root	-6.1959	0.0000	d = 0

Source: Calculated by the authors

Table 1 shows that the results of the Unit root test show that with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05\%$, the hypothesis H_0 about the existence of a unit root is rejected, so the series ROA, ROE, LA, NII, BIS, and MBS all stop. The PVAR model, according to GMM regression, is selected for regression. Besides, a unit root (i.e., non-stationarity) is the null hypothesis for any series. Table 1 shows that the data demonstrate that all variables (ROA, ROE, LA, NII, BIS, and MBS) have statistically significant negative t-statistics (p-values (Prob.*) of 0.0000). All the series are stationary at their respective levels ($d = 0$), as the null hypothesis of a unit root is rejected at the significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ (Borio, 2020; Moudud-Ul-Huq et al., 2018; Mateev et al., 2022).

These results imply that the time series data for ROA, ROE, LA, NII, BIS, and MBS are sufficient for additional econometric analysis, like the PVAR model, without needing differencing to attain stationarity.

Table 2: Testing the optimal lag selection for the model

Lag	CD	J	J P value	MBIC	MAIC	MQIC
1	0.9999	115.4271	0.2948	-539.2102	-100.5729	-273.7941
2	0.9999	76.26274	0.3431	-360.1622	-67.73726	-183.2181
3	0.9999	22.96146	0.9548	-195.251	-49.03854	-106.779
4	0.9999	-	-	-	-	-

Source: Calculated by the authors

Testing the optimal lag selection for the model, this study used the criteria MBIC, MAIC, and MQIC to determine the optimal delay for the model: $p = 1$, described in Table 2. Moreover, Table

2 displays the outcomes of experiments that tested different lag selection criteria for the PVAR model, including MBIC, MAIC, and MQIC (Modified Quasi Information Criterion). To capture the dynamic interactions between the variables, it is crucial to add lags in the model; this test will help you decide the best number of lags to include. Significant information from Table 2 showed that the first Lag, with an MBIC of -539.2102, an MAIC of -100.5729, and an MQIC of -273.7941, are the lowest numbers for lag 1. With a J-test statistic of 115.4271 and a p-value of 0.2948263, there appears to be a decent fit. It seems that lags 2 and 3 may not offer a better model fit than lag 1 because MBIC, MAIC, and MQIC values rise (become less negative) with increasing lag numbers. Both lag 2 and lag 3 have greater MBIC values than lag 1, with -360.1622 and -195.251, respectively (Duho et al., 2021; Belás et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2020). There are no findings for lag 4, which could mean that the test stopped after three lags, probably because lag 1 was already shown to be the best lag. To reduce MBIC, MAIC, and MQIC while maintaining a decent balance between model complexity and goodness of fit, the data in Table 2 indicate that lag 1 is the best for the PVAR model.

The Granger causality test results show that the model variables (ROA, ROE, LA, NII, BIS, and MBS) are significantly related. Evaluating both variables in the PVAR model is vital to understanding how digital transformation and income diversification affect banks' profitability and performance. This confirms that they are interconnected in Table 3.

Table 3: Results of Causal tests of ROA, ROE, LA, NII, BIS, MBS

	Equation\Excluded	chi2	df	Prob > chi2
ROA	ROE	2.571	1	0.010
	LA	0.319	1	0.057
	NII	0.076	1	0.078
	BIS	0.240	1	0.062
	MBS	0.433	1	0.051
	ALL	9.472	5	0.009
ROE	ROA	14.864	1	0.000
	LA	0.661	1	0.041
	NII	0.190	1	0.066
	BIS	0.139	1	0.070
	MBS	2.183	1	0.014
	ALL	25.849	5	0.000
LA	ROA	0.138	1	0.071
	ROE	1.562	1	0.021
	NII	1.224	1	0.026
	BIS	23.968	1	0.000
	MBS	1.898	1	0.016
	ALL	25.717	5	0.000
NII	ROA	1.620	1	0.020
	ROE	1.016	1	0.031
	LA	1.900	1	0.016

	BIS	0.361	1	0.054
	MBS	0.309	1	0.057
	ALL	4.011	5	0.054
BIS				
	ROA	0.301	1	0.058
	ROE	1.286	1	0.025
	LA	0.404	1	0.052
	NII	0.084	1	0.077
	MBS	2.143	1	0.014
	ALL	4.135	5	0.053
MBS				
	ROA	0.051	1	0.082
	ROE	0.387	1	0.053
	LA	1.187	1	0.027
	NII	1.912	1	0.016
	BIS	0.349	1	0.055
	ALL	2.666	5	0.075

Source: Calculated by the authors

Table 3 shows a statistical model using the Granger causality test to determine whether one time series can predict another. In this study, the test examines whether the variables (ROA, ROE, LA, NII, BIS, and MBS) have a causal relationship. The results are presented using the chi-squared (χ^2) statistic, degrees of freedom (df), and the p-values for each test.

The findings of the Granger causality test with ROA (Return on Assets) show that ROE, LA, NII, BIS, and MBS are all causally related to ROA. This is supported by p-values that are less than the significance level of 0.05, which means that changes in these variables impact ROA. A high causal impact on ROA is suggested by the chi-squared statistic for ROE (2.571, $p = 0.010$) and for ALL factors (9.472, $p = 0.009$) (Mateev et al., 2022; Khan et al., 2017). The correlation between ROE and Return on Equity (ROA) is highly significant ($p = 0.000$), and with MBS, it is even stronger ($p = 0.014$). A weak but substantial causal link (p-values between 0.041 and 0.070) exists between other variables (NII, BIS, and LA). LA (Liquid Assets): Return on equity (ROE) and mortgage-backed securities (MBS) show a strong causal relationship with LA (p-values of 0.021 and 0.016, respectively). Overall, the model significantly impacts LA, as shown by the chi-squared statistic of 25.717 ($p = 0.000$) for ALL factors combined. Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), and Mortgage-Backed Securities (MBS) all significantly affect Non-Interest Income (NII), with p-values of 0.020, 0.031, and 0.016, respectively. A substantial causal link with NII is also shown by the test for ALL variables ($p = 0.054$), indicating that non-interest income is affected by changes in other factors. With p-values of 0.025, 0.014, and 0.052, respectively, ROE, MBS, and LA significantly impact BIS (Broadband Internet Subscribers). The overall test for ALL variables indicates a marginally significant association with $p = 0.053$ (AlKhouri & Arouri, 2019; Mirzaei et al., 2024). The results show that at the significance level, $\alpha = 0.05$, the chains ROA, ROE, LA, NII, BIS, and MBS all have a causal impact on each other. Thus, the above results show that the variables included in the model are all necessary for the model.

Check the stability of the model

Table 4: Eigenvalue stability condition test

Eigenvalue		
Real	Imaginary	Modulus
0.8793247	0	0.8793247
0.7579196	0	0.7579196
0.7351989	0.101433	0.7421631
0.7351989	-0.101433	0.7421631
0.0919316	0.106719	0.1408558
0.0919316	-0.106719	0.1408558

Source: Calculated by the authors

To test the stability of the PVAR model, use the AR Root Test to check that the roots or eigenvalues are all less than 1 or are all within the unit circle, then the PVAR model achieves stability. It is described in Table 4. All the eigenvalues lie inside the unit circle. PVAR satisfies stability conditions. The model is stable since every eigenvalue is contained in the unit circle. As a result, the analysis's reliance on the PVAR model to examine the time-dependent interactions of ROA, ROE, LA, NII, BIS, and MBS can be assured of stable and trustworthy results (Syadullah, 2018; Kasman & Kasman, 2016). This is because the moduli of all eigenvalues are less than 1, indicating they are within the unit circle. The stability of the model is guaranteed by the maximal modulus value of 0.8793247, which is significantly lower than 1.

The research results show that investment in information technology positively impacts banks' profits. It is described in Table 4. Information technology investment also has a positive impact on non-interest income. High information technology systems will also increase bank income, especially non-interest income, and ultimately increase bank profits. However, digitalization has a positive impact on non-interest income but a negligible impact on profits for Asian banks (Kozak, 2021; Li et al., 2021; Syadullah, 2018). This shows that digitalization increases non-interest income, but the operating costs of digitalization are still relatively high, so revenue from digitalization and operating costs are still relatively balanced; thus, the contribution of digitalization to profits and Asian banks is insignificant.

Discussion of Findings

The impact of income diversification and digital economic change on the profitability of Asian banks is discussed in the study's conclusions. Here are a few essential takeaways from the empirical analysis that was conducted using the PVAR model and GMM regression, along with an explanation of the findings:

- (1) Effects of the digital revolution on unearned amounts based on the results indicate that banks' non-interest income is positively affected by digital transformation. Online banking, mobile payment systems, and other diversification services made possible by banks' investments in digital technology are growing non-interest revenue streams (Acharya & Steffen, 2020; Mirzaei et al., 2024). However, the study notes that digital transformation can significantly influence overall profitability in the long run, especially in the beginning phases when operational costs are high.

Upgrading technological infrastructure and maintaining secure digital platforms is expensive for banks. Because of these hefty expenses, the net impact on profitability is minimal despite digital transformation improving non-interest revenue.

(2) Importance of diversified income streams in mitigating risk: This study's results support the idea that banks can lessen their exposure to interest income risk by diversifying their revenue streams. To protect themselves from declines in credit-based activity, banks might diversify their services to include remittances, transactions, and wealth management. According to the study's support for company performance, banks' overall competitiveness and performance are enhanced by income diversification (Moudud-Ul-Huq et al., 2018; Kasman & Kasman, 2016). Banks in emerging nations, such as Malaysia, Indonesia, and Thailand, have improved their risk management and company performance by diversifying their income streams. Although diversity lowers risk for individual banks, it may raise sector-wide systemic risk, particularly in times of financial crisis, according to previous studies included in this one.

(3) Banks confront new problems, especially in cybersecurity, as they embrace digital platforms, according to the report. This poses a systemic risk. Banks risk having their operations and reputations compromised due to fraud and data breaches (Mateev et al., 2022). Because of this, digital transformation initiatives should take a back seat to investments in cybersecurity. The growing interconnectedness of the world's financial systems puts Asian banks and the financial technologies they use in greater danger of cyberattacks and other systemic disasters. Thus, financial institutions need plans to enhance digital offerings while mitigating risks.

(4) Digital transformation increases non-interest income but has little impact on net profitability, leading to mixed findings regarding profitability based on non-interest income gains. This is because there is a delicate balance to be struck between the high costs of developing and sustaining cutting-edge technology and the income from digital services (Addai et al., 2022; AlKhouri & Arouri, 2019). Although the findings indicate that the initial expenses may restrict the short-term impact on profitability, banks are expected to have long-term gains as they optimize their digital operations and decrease associated costs.

These implications show that while geographical considerations and market maturity levels vary, the study's research of Asian banks' lessons is essential for financial institutions seeking worldwide digital transformation and income diversification.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study found that Asian banks' profitability and competitiveness depend on digital transformation and income diversification, although high investment costs and risks minimize their immediate impact on earnings. The analysis suggests banks' digital transformation should prioritize long-term profitability, customer-centricity, and risk management. Diversifying banks' income globally to boost business performance and risk management has driven business operations transformation and economic digitization. Diversifying income sources, especially non-interest, is inevitable for banks. Banks must use digital technology platforms for non-interest income to supply products and services swiftly and conveniently. Banks can enhance cash flow and income by diversifying risks. Digital transformation presents many problems for banks

balancing technology investment costs and business outcomes. Digital transformation must be safe, and consumer data protection is paramount. To create a sustainable financial system, banks must carefully diversify income sources on their digital transformation platforms, notably non-interest income. Commercial banks can improve their products and services and become more competitive by better understanding digital technology:

First, financial institutions must plan long-term digital transformation to meet profitability goals. Planning technology spending and efficient digital infrastructure are crucial to this process. Financial authorities and governments should collaborate to encourage digital banking developments while controlling costs. Banks that invest in Fintech may receive tax breaks or low-interest loans. Policymakers should push banks to adopt scalable technology that reduces initial investment and maximises ROI. Public-private partnerships or government-funded research programs could produce efficient and cheap digital banking systems.

Second, banks should prioritise customer-focused digital platforms. Better customer service increases digital service use and revenue. Governments should encourage banks to diversify their income streams by expanding their non-interest services. New products and innovations in digital payments, wealth management, and fintech collaborations may qualify banks for government subsidies or grants. Regulatory bodies urge conventional banks and fintech startups to collaborate. Banks can enhance profitability and diversify income with regulators' regulatory sandbox and simplified approval processes for fintech integration.

Finally, banks must protect their digital platforms from cyberattacks and conduct strong risk management to reduce systemic risk. Policymakers should ensure that banks' diversification plans don't threaten the financial sector's stability. To maintain banks' revenue mix consistent and not overemphasize potentially risky non-interest income streams, authorities may need to monitor the non-interest income ratio. Additionally, governments should facilitate cross-border collaboration amongst regional banks to share technological advances and best practices. Asian banks may increase safety and profitability by setting regional digital banking, cybersecurity, and data exchange standards.

Limitations and future research: The study may have missed essential developments, especially in the ever-changing digital ecosystem, because it used data from 39 Asian countries from 2006 to 2021. The lack of uniform and high-quality data across nations may make the study erroneous. This study investigates how the digital revolution affects business today. Neglecting digital investments' long-term effects, which might take years, may undervalue digitalization's benefits. Considering technical innovation and adaptability, future studies should evaluate how digital transformation affects banks' bottom lines over time. Banking digitalization may be separated from non-interest revenue components, and their profitability and risk mitigation contributions should be studied based on transaction fees, wealth management, and digital banking.

Acknowledgments: The author acknowledges being supported by the University of Finance – Marketing, Vietnam.

References

- Acharya, V. V., & Steffen, S. (2020). The risk of being a fallen angel and the corporate dash for cash in the midst of COVID. *The Review of Corporate Finance Studies*, 9(3), 430–471. <https://doi.org/10.1093/rcfs/cfaa013>.
- Addai, B., Tang, W., & Agyeman, A. S. (2022). Examining the impact of income diversification on bank performance: Are foreign banks heterogeneous?. *Journal of Applied Economics*, 25(1), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15140326.2021.2022828>.
- Aguayo, Z. F., & Ślusarczyk, B. (2020). Risks of banking services' digitalization: The practice of diversification and sustainable development goals. *Sustainability*, 12(10), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12104040>.
- AlKhoury, R., & Arouri, H. (2019). The effect of diversification on risk and return in banking sector: Evidence from the Gulf Cooperation Council countries. *International Journal of Managerial Finance*, 15(1), 100–128. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijmf-01-2018-0024>.
- Belás, J., Korauš, M., Kombo, F., & Korauš, A. (2016). Electronic banking security and customer satisfaction in commercial banks. *Journal of Security and Sustainability Issues*, 5(3), 411–422. [https://doi.org/10.9770/jssi.2016.5.3\(9\)](https://doi.org/10.9770/jssi.2016.5.3(9)).
- Bömer, M., & Maxin, H. (2018). Why fintechs cooperate with banks - Evidence from Germany. *Hannover Economic Papers*, 107(637), 359–386. <https://www.econstor.eu/handle/10419/200649>.
- Borio, C. (2020). The Covid-19 economic crisis: Dangerously unique. *Business Economics*, 55(4), 181–190. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s11369-020-00184-2>.
- Duho, K. C. T., Duho, D. M., & Forson, J. A. (2021). Impact of income diversification strategies on credit risk and market risk among microfinance institutions. *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*, 39(2), 523–546. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jeas-09-2020-0166>.
- Duho, K. C. T., Onumah, J. M., & Owodo, R. A. (2019). Bank diversification and performance in an emerging market. *International Journal of Managerial Finance*, 16(1), 120–138. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJMF-04-2019-0137>.
- Kasman, A., & Kasman, S. (2016). Bank size, competition, and risk in the Turkish banking industry. *Empirica*, 43(3), 607–631. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10663-015-9307-1>.
- Khan, S. J. M., Samsudin, S., & Islam, R. (2017). Efficiency of banks in Southeast Asia: Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines and Thailand. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 44(12), 2302–2312. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSE-01-2016-0020>.
- Kozak, S. (2021). The impact of COVID-19 on bank equity and performance: The case of Central Eastern South European countries. *Sustainability*, 13(19), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su131911036>.
- Li, J., Ding, H., Hu, Y., & Wan, G. (2021). Dealing with dynamic endogeneity in international business research. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 52(3), 339–362. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41267-020-00398-8>.
- Mateev, M., Moudud-UI-Huq, S., Sahyouni, A., & Tariq, M. U. (2022). Capital regulation, competition and risk-taking: Policy implications for banking sector stability in the MENA region. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 60(4), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2021.101579>.

- Mawutor, K. M. J., Boadi, I., Antwi, S., & Tetteh, A. B. (2023). Improving banks' profitability through income diversification and intellectual capital: The sub-Saharan Africa perspective. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 11(2), 1–35. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2023.2271658>.
- Mirzaei, A., Saad, M. & Emrouznejad, A. (2024). Bank stock performance during the COVID-19 crisis: Does efficiency explain why Islamic banks fared relatively better?. *Annals of Operations Research*, 334(3), 317–355. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-022-04600-y>.
- Moudud-Ul-Huq, S., Ashraf, B. N., Gupta, A. D., & Zheng, C. (2018). Does bank diversification heterogeneously affect performance and risk-taking in ASEAN emerging economies?. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 46(12), 342–362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2018.04.007>.
- Öhman, P., & Yazdanfar, D. (2018). Organizational-level profitability determinants in commercial banks: Swedish evidence. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 45(6), 1175–1191. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JES-07-2017-0182>.
- Syadullah, M. (2018). ASEAN banking efficiency review facing financial services liberalization: The Indonesian perspective. *Asian Development Policy Review*, 6(2), 88–99. <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.107.2018.62.88.99>.
- Yang, H. F., Liu, C. L., & Chou, R. Y. (2020). Bank diversification and systemic risk. *The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance*, 77(8), 311–326. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.qref.2019.11.003>.